

Investigation of low temperature plasmas formed in low density gases surrounding laser produced plasmas

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Abstract. Low temperature plasma production is possible as a result of photoionization using high-intensity EUV (Extreme UltraViolet) and SXR (Soft X-Ray) pulses. Plasma of this type is also present in outer space, e.g. aurora borealis, it also occurs when high velocity objects enter the atmosphere, where high temperatures can be produced locally by friction. The low temperature plasma is also formed in an ambient gas surrounding the hot laser produced plasma (LPP). In this work a special system has been prepared for investigation of this type of plasma. The LPP was created inside a chamber filled with a gas under a low pressure, of the order of 1 – 50 mbar, by the laser pulse [3-9 J], [1-8 ns] focused onto a gas puff target. In such a case, the SXR/EUV radiation emitted from the LPP was partially absorbed in the low density gas. In this case high and low temperature plasmas ($T_e \sim 100$ eV, $T_e \sim 1$ eV respectively) were created locally in the chamber. Investigation of the EUV induced plasmas were performed mainly using spectral methods in UV/VIS light. The measurements were performed using an echelle spectrometer and additionally spatial-temporal measurements were performed employing an optical streak camera. Spectral analysis was supported by the PGOPHER numerical code.

Keywords: plasma, photoionization, laser plasma, low pressure, SXR, EUV.

Introduction

The formation of chemical compounds or individual molecules is an indispensable element of nature. It is important to know what conditions are conducive to the formation of specific chemical compounds. In the case of plasma this requires exceeding of the ionization, excitation or dissociation energies. They are different for each elements/molecules, and these energies usually start at a few eV. Various species are created this way. It can lead to formation of new molecular species, not existing in the initial gaseous mixture. The molecular species can be stable or transient. Their formation requires suitable plasma conditions.

Such processes can be induced by extreme ultraviolet (EUV) or soft X-ray (SXR) radiation. In normal terrestrial conditions we do not encounter this radiation. It stops in the upper parts of the atmosphere, ionizing its components. It can lead to escape of particles from the planet's atmosphere or contribute to the molecular processes mentioned above. Similar processes may occur on other planets or moons with their own atmospheres [1], [2], especially taking into account the ubiquitous presence of this type of radiation in space, e.g. of stellar origin, including the Sun. The formation of molecules under such conditions can lead to more complex structures, including the foundations of life [3]. Another phenomenon that can cause ionization of both interstellar dust and the atmosphere of the celestial body is the entry of a meteor into it [4].

Many laboratory solutions can be used to obtain atomic, ionic or molecular processes. EUV or SXR radiation can be produced in various ways. One way to get a broad spectrum from X-rays to infrared (IR) is through synchrotron systems, but it is an expensive and

complex set-up, another is free electron lasers (FEL), and yet another plasma source. Plasma sources include those based on high-power discharge (DPP) or laser produced plasmas (LPP).

In this work, the LPP source was used to generate radiation in the EUV / SXR range. Such solutions have been used many times to generate this type of radiation [5]. Thanks to such a source, which uses a gas target, various gas mixtures, suitably prepared in advance, can be used. They can include simple molecular gases, e.g. nitrogen, and more complex mixtures of various gases, e.g. a mixture of krypton, sulfur, fluorine and helium. This solution allows the observation of the formation of new particles as a result of the interaction of the gases used with radiation from the LPP source.

Experimental Setup

The experimental system Fig.1 consists of a small vacuum chamber that can be filled with the investigated gas mixture under low pressure (1-50 mbar). The system shown in Fig.1 can be divided into two parts: the first one designed for production of the LPPs and the second one dedicated for the investigation of low-temperature plasmas formed around the LPP. The LPPs were formed using a Nd:YAG laser which was focused onto a gas puff target. The target consists of the identical gas mixture that fills the chamber, but its density was much higher, close to the atmospheric density ($\sim 10^{19} \text{cm}^{-3}$). The second system allows for measurements of the UV/VIS radiation emitted from plasmas produced by the LPP source. Measurements are carried out using an optical spectrometer and streak camera.

The LPP source was based on the Nd:YAG NL laser system 129 - EXPLA and the gas puff target system. The laser system with a wavelength of $\lambda = 1064 \text{ nm}$ can provide energy in the range 1-10 J (3-9 J in this experiment), pulse time duration $t = 1$ or 10 ns (1-2 ns in short pulse and 5-10 ns in long pulse regime), repetition rate $f = 10 \text{ Hz}$, laser beam diameter 25 mm

(top-hat intensity distribution). The laser beam is focused onto the gas puff target using a plano-convex lens. The resulting intensity reached 10^{14} W/cm² or $2 \cdot 10^{13}$ W/cm² for short and long pulse regimes respectively. In such conditions a hot plasma is generated directly above the nozzle of the gas valve. The ambient gas filling the chamber is converted to a low temperature plasma due to exposure to various factors accompanying the LPP formation.

An optical emission of excited molecules and ions that arise in the vicinity of the laser plasma was investigated in a wide spectral range (200-780 nm) using the ESA 4000 echelle spectrometer (LLA Instruments GmbH & Co KG, Berlin, Germany). The spectrometer is equipped with an ICCD camera with a Kodak KAF 1001 detector (spectral resolution of the system was about $\lambda / \Delta\lambda \sim 20000$) [6]. A diameter of the acquisition region is limited by the collecting optical system, approximately 1 mm FWHM in a focal point of the collecting system. The light was acquired at a distance of 6 mm from the LPP. In order to investigate the behavior of the low temperature plasma, spatial-temporal measurements were carried out. They were made by an optical streak camera (Hamamatsu C10910). The optical axis of the streak camera was perpendicular to the axis of the laser beam as shown in Fig.1. Between the entrance slit of the camera and the plasma position a focusing lens was mounted. It allowed to form a plasma image in a plane of the entrance slit. Changing the position of the lens it was possible to select a narrow observation region at various distances above the LPP.

In order to prepare gas mixtures, a special system was constructed Fig.2. It was aimed at creating a mixture to fill the chamber and form the gas puff target. In this work, noble and molecular gases such as: Kr, Xe, Ar, He, Ne, H_2 , N_2 , CO_2 , SF_6 were used to create the mixtures.

Experimental Results

Spatial-temporal measurements

Spatial-temporal measurements using the optical streak camera were made for various conditions of the low temperature plasma formation. At first, comparative studies of argon plasmas induced in a vicinity of the LPP, under different conditions were performed. LPPs were created in the gas puff target, formed in a chamber remaining under a low vacuum 5×10^{-1} mbar or a low pressure of argon ~ 1.3 mbar. In our experiments the term low vacuum means a pressure maintained in the vacuum chamber by a roughing pump. The low pressure was obtained by controlled injection of a gas into the chamber. The laser was operating in a long-pulse regime with a pulse energy of ~ 3.9 J. The investigated area was located 6.6 mm above the LPP source. Importantly, the radiation recorded in the streak camera images refers to EUV/SXR radiation from the laser plasma. The dark area on the y-axis (time) is the time needed to synchronize the laser with the triggering of the streak camera. In Fig.3, streak images for such parameters are shown. In both cases spatial distribution of the optical emission selected by a narrow slit is visible as a function of time. Maximum of the intensity profile taken along the time axis can be noticed after approximately ~ 80 ns from the beginning of the emission. The corresponding FWHM is ~ 110 ns. After the next ~ 700 ns a second maximum appears with a FWHM of ~ 250 ns. These parameters are similar in both cases. An important difference concerns the relative intensities for the profiles. Intensity of both maxima recorded for plasmas created under low vacuum conditions, are lower than the corresponding intensities obtained for plasmas induced under the low ambient pressure. These maxima are on the same intensity scale.

The influence of pressure on the optical emission of plasmas induced in the ambient gas was also investigated. Measurements were conducted for nitrogen plasmas created in a chamber filled with nitrogen at various pressures: 2.5, 5 and 10 mbar (Fig.4). The observed

region, as in the case of argon, was 6.6 mm above the LPP source, and the streak camera entrance slit was set at 60 μm . The laser was operating in a short-pulse regime with a pulse energy of ~ 7.5 J. As can be seen in Fig.4 a) at the ambient pressure of 2.5 mbar, intensity is strong, but only for the first 250 ns after start of the laser pulse. The same is true in higher pressures, for which after this time the intensity is still high enough to be seen in the pictures. The FWHM for the regions located 5 mm from the nozzle axis in a horizontal direction (1 mm and 12 mm in the X axis), for each pressure is about 60 ns, and in the central area, above the nozzle about 120 ns. In addition, the difference between these images is the relative intensity. It concerns especially the second maximum visible at a time about 600ns from the beginning of emission. For plasmas created in the ambient gas with a pressure of 10 mbar it is almost twice as high as for 2.5 mbar.

It is also worth looking at how the change of the observation region over the LPP source affects the time-space distribution. Figure 5 shows the streak images recorded for three different distances over the LPP: 2.8 mm, 6.6 mm and 8.5 mm respectively. The wider scale makes it possible to observe the formation of high intensity regions, which widen with distance. In addition, an interesting phenomenon is the occurrence of increased intensity after some time. This is clearly seen in Fig.5 b), 0.6 μs from of the start of the registration process. In Fig.5 c), where the distance from LPP is the greatest - this intensity area becomes more blurry.

Molecular measurements

The aim of the measurements with the use of the echelle spectrometer was to determine whether it is possible to find molecular spectra in the range of 200-780 nm for the system with the LPP source. The most representative and intense in the studied range were

diatomic molecules. Molecular bands expected in this range were carbon compounds and excimers, hence the prepared mixtures contained selected noble gases CO_2 and N_2 [7-10]. The measurement results presented in Fig.6 come from the study of the region located 6 mm above the LPP source and the spectra were observed in different time moments of the low-temperature plasma existence, up to 200 ns after creation of the LPPs. These measurements were performed for a mixture consisting of [2% SF_6 , 18% Xe and 80% He], and the ambient pressure of about 10 mbar and acquisition window 100 ns. The visible molecular spectra belong to the XeF excimer and it corresponds to a transitions $D(^2\Pi_{1/2}) - X(^2\Sigma)$ and $B(^2\Pi_{1/2}) - X(^2\Sigma)$ [8-9]. The formation process of these molecules is very short, of the order of 200 ns. Investigation has also been carried out in the same conditions, for a mixture of [4% SF_6 , 16% Kr and 80% He]. The KrF excimer spectra were obtained and are shown in Fig.7 [9-10] with transitions described as $D(^2\Pi_{1/2}) - X(^2\Sigma)$ and $B(^2\Sigma_{1/2}) - X(^2\Sigma)$. Investigated region was located 6 mm above the LPP source and observed for different times of plasma propagation. The formation time of KrF molecules is similar to that of XeF molecules. The formation of some molecules such as excimers is extremely short. The process is of the order of a few several hundred ns.

Similar measurements were performed for mixtures containing molecular gases N_2 and CO_2 , ambient pressure of about 10 mbar and acquisition window 1000 ns. Using such mixtures, except the N_2 and CO_2 molecular bands, spectra corresponding to the CN species were also recorded. These spectra, however, were very weak, hence, Xe admixture was added. In Fig.8a a CN band spectrum recorded for a gas mixture composed of 10% Xe, 10% N_2 and 80% CO_2 is shown.

Discussion of the results

This work is based on the study of low-temperature plasmas induced in gas mixtures. Using various gas mixtures parameters both as an injected mixture and as a mixture filling of the chamber, the formation of new molecules, i.e., not constituting the components of the pre-mixture, was observed. This experiment showed that the LPP source is able to provide conditions for the formation of molecules and their registration using spectral methods.

Based on the pictures presented in Fig.3, it can be concluded that the radiation propagation from the LPP source depends on the conditions in the chamber. Low vacuum causes fewer acts of photoionization and ionization than in a chamber filled with gas under low pressure. It is worth noting that in the images from the streak camera in the near area above the nozzle we are observing a visibly lower intensity than in the diagonal direction. This is due to the fact that the SXR radiation is strongly absorbed near the LPP source, therefore it can hardly propagate in the gas injection path. On the other hand, at the border of the injected gas with the ambient gas, this radiation can propagate and ionize the gas. The resulting low-temperature plasma emits the light that is visible as intense maxima on the right and left side of the streak images [12]. Optical radiation recorded for the central area above the LPP, occurring at a time of approximately 600 ns (Fig.4-5) cannot be induced by the EUV/SXR radiation. At this time the hot and dense plasma emitting the energetic photons does not exist. The emission maximum recorded after such long time could be a result of the shock wave propagation or the low temperature plasma formation by fast ions or electrons from the LPP. A detailed analysis concerning occurrence of this emission maximum supported by the corresponding numerical simulations were reported in ref. [12].

Except spatial-temporal, also spectral measurements in the optical range were performed. Contrary to the atomic spectra, molecular ones are composed from bands,

corresponding to molecular electronic transitions. Such spectra can be simulated using one of the available numerical codes, e.g. PGOPHER [13], To perform the simulations for a specific molecule the necessary vibration and rotational constants have to be applied. Due to the fact that real molecules have anharmonic potentials, energies of the vibration levels have to be calculated based on the formula (1).

$$(1) E(v) = T_e + \omega_e(v + 1/2) - \omega_e x_e (v + 1/2)^2 + \omega_e y_e (v + 1/2)^3 + \dots$$

Where, v is vibrational quantum number, T_e is minimum electronic energy cm^{-1} , ω_e - first vibrational term cm^{-1} , $\omega_e x_e$ - second vibrational term cm^{-1} , $\omega_e y_e$ - third vibrational term cm^{-1} . If we consider a molecule with an anharmonic potential, the rotational constant changes slightly with vibrational state. The rotational constant B_v for a given vibrational state can be described by the expression (2).

$$(2) B_v = B_e - \alpha_e(v + 1/2) + \gamma_e(v + 1/2)^2 + \dots$$

Where, B_e is rotational constant in equilibrium position cm^{-1} , α_e - first rotational term cm^{-1} , γ_e - rotation-vibration interaction constant cm^{-1} .

The necessary molecular constants can be found in the NIST database [11].

The simulation results for CN molecules were compared with the spectral observations using the mixture: [10% Xe, 10% N_2 and 80% CO_2] and are shown in Fig.8. Transitions for selected spectra come from states $B^2\Sigma^+ - X^2\Sigma^+$. As you can see, the simulations reflect the nature of the observations quite well. The process of CN molecules formation is much longer than that of excimer molecules – compare Fig.8 and Fig.9. Their formation lasts for tens μs .

Summary

In this work, emission of LPP formed in low pressure ambient gas from the gas puff target was studied. As part of this work, the research was divided into those that used

streak cameras spatial-temporal measurements, and spectroscopic measurements of molecular spectra. The analysis of images from the streak camera allowed to examine the nature of radiation emission and the regions where the expected emission is the highest. Which in turn contributed to the registration of molecular spectra, along with their subsequent analysis and simulations in numerical programs. The found excimers are interesting spectra, the time in which they were created was a few several hundred ns. These studies provide the basis for further molecular analyzes in such a system, as well as premises for analyzes in wider spectral ranges, e.g. in infrared.

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Fig.1 Schematic view of the experimental system for time-space measurements using an optical streak camera and spectral measurements using an echelle spectrometer for a laser produced plasma.

Fig.2 A special system for mixing noble and molecular gases.

Fig.3 Spatial-temporal distribution for argon laser produced plasma. The observation area was 6.6 mm above the LPP source a) low vacuum environment 5×10^{-1} mbar, b) low argon ambient pressure ~ 1.3 mbar.

Fig.4 The spatial-temporal distribution of the intensity obtained from the streak camera for a height of 6.6 mm above the LPP source and different pressures. The chamber was filled with nitrogen, pressure in the chamber a) 2.5 mbar, b) 5 mbar, c) 10 mbar.

Fig.5 Spatial-temporal distribution in different time scale and heights a) height of 2.8 mm (timescale of 200 ns), b) 6.6 mm (1 μ s) and c) 8.5 mm (2 μ s).

Fig.6 Spectra from XeF transitions $D(^2\Pi_{1/2}) - X(^2\Sigma)$ and $B(^2\Pi_{1/2}) - X(^2\Sigma)$ area located 6 mm above the LPP source and observed in different moments of the radiation propagation process: a) start of the process b) 100 ns after the process start and c) 200 ns after the process start.

Fig.7 Spectra from KrF transitions $D(^2\Pi_{1/2}) - X(^2\Sigma)$ and $B(^2\Sigma_{1/2}) - X(^2\Sigma)$ for a mixture of gases: 2% SF_6 , 18% Xe, 80% He. Investigated region was located 6mm above the LPP source and observed in different moments of the radiation propagation process a) start of the process b) 50 ns after the process start, c) 100 ns later d) 150 ns later and e) 200 ns after the process start.

Fig.8 Comparison of the spectrum obtained from the simulation in the PGOPHER program (right) with the measurement made with the Echelle spectrometer for states $B^2\Sigma^+ - X^2\Sigma^+$ (left) for CN molecules.

Fig.9 Spectra showing the duration of CN molecule formation processes a) start of the process, b) 53 μ s later. c) 63 μ s later.